

FOSTERING ZERO-WASTE INITIATIVE FOR STUDENTS: ENVIRONMENTAL LITERACY AND ACHIEVEMENT

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Fostering Zero-Waste Initiative for Students: Environmental Literacy and Achievement

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Abstract

Solid waste generation is increasing due to the rise in worldwide population, which causes major environmental harm. This paper examined zero-waste initiative and how it affects student environmental literacy and achievement. The study used percentage, mean, simple linear regression analysis, and MANOVA. The researcher employed a quantitative methods research design supported by a qualitative data to investigate participant-suggested interventions, environmental literacy, environmental achievement scores, and student involvement in program implementation. Respondents were chosen by stratified sampling. In response to qualitative component, it was accomplished via purposive sampling. The study found that students regularly engaged in the zero-waste program's implementation. Additionally, driving students' support was their realization of the program's importance. Furthermore, the findings revealed a generally average degree of environmental literacy achievement. Further, the survey revealed that Lambayong National High School's students support the zero-waste initiative, therefore displaying environmental literacy in solid waste management both inside and outside of the institution. Thus, it is advised to guarantee the sustainability of the initiative by means of better organization, enhanced LGU support, and promotion of cooperation between the institution and the society in waste management projects.

Keywords: *environmental attitude, environmental knowledge, environmental literacy, environmental practices, zero-waste initiative*

Introduction

The increasing amount of solid waste in schools has become a major global issue, generating environmental damage and dangerous consequences. As World Bank (2020) reported that over 2.01 billion tons of municipal solid waste are generated every year, 20% is recycled and composted while 33% being thrown of inappropriately.

As of 2018, the garbage volume in the Philippines reached 16.6 million tons, positioning it as the "third-largest generator of solid waste annually among Southeast Asian countries" (Romero, 2020). The rising generation of solid waste as a result of rapid population growth has become a major global issue, generating environmental damage and dangerous consequences. Waste is a byproduct of the human life cycle and can take many forms, this includes biological waste, hazardous waste, solid waste, and technological garbage (The Environmental Literacy Council, 2015). Solid waste constitutes a major category of refuse created worldwide, characterised as undesirable and discarded items resulting from everyday human activities (Mishra et al., 2014). Solid waste and its management are now recognized as global challenges (Singh et al., 2014). Yard garbage, food waste, plastics, wood, metals, paper, rubber, leather, batteries, inert materials, textiles, paint containers, demolition and construction debris, and other difficult-to-classify items are included (Abdel-Shafy and Mansour, 2018).

According to the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR)-XII "2022 Ecological Solid Waste Management Status Report," the Province of South Cotabato, including General Santos City, generates the most waste among the four (4) provinces in Region 12, followed by the Province of North Cotabato, Sultan Kudarat, and Sarangani, in that order. The sole city in Sultan Kudarat Province which is the LGU Tacurong, produces the most trash; LGU Esperanza produces the least.

The Zero-Waste Program Initiative at Lambayong National High School was initiated seven months ago. This relates to the RA 9003 and the DepEd Sultan Kudarat Division Memorandum No. 53, s. 2024, which entered into effect on March 12, 2024, on the "No to Single-use Plastic Policy," which aims to create green and clean offices and educational environments, described in DepEd Order No. 5 s. 2014 "Implementing Guidelines on Integrating Gulayan sa Paaralan, SWM, and Tree Planting under the National Greening Program" aims to promote environmental stewardship in pupils and foster a culture of waste reduction and recycling. This study evaluates student environmental awareness and the efficacy of the Zero-Waste Program. This study was examined the program's strengths and limitations in order to improve its effectiveness and promote environmental sustainability.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aims to assess the influence of Zero-Waste Program implementation to the students' environmental literacy. Specifically, it will seek to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of Zero-Waste Program Implementation in terms of Student Participation in their classroom?
2. What is the extent of student's environmental literacy in terms of:
 - 2.1. environmental knowledge;
 - 2.2. environmental attitude; and
 - 2.3. environmental practices?

3. What is the level of student's achievement on their environmental literacy?
4. Can student participation significantly predict their level of achievement on environmental literacy?
5. Is the extent of the zero-waste program on students' participation significantly correlates to their environmental literacy in terms of their environmental knowledge, attitude, and practices?
6. Does the extent of students' participation in the Zero-Waste Program significantly contribute to their environmental literacy, specifically in terms of their environmental knowledge, attitudes, and practices?
7. Based on the student's environmental literacy result, what strategic outcomes or desired interventions do you suggest to improve the program in terms of:
 - 7.1. school community;
 - 7.2. government;
 - 7.3. students; and
 - 7.4. self?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a quantitative methods research design supported by qualitative data, wherein qualitative and quantitative data were collected concurrently but analyzed separately. The results were then compared and combined to draw overall conclusions. Interviews and surveys were conducted simultaneously. Creswell and Plano Clark (2011) defined this design as a research methodology that includes the simultaneous collection and analysis of qualitative and quantitative data, enabling researchers to gain a thorough understanding of the research problem.

In this study, only one group of students was exposed to the Zero-Waste Program. Respondents evaluated the program, and their environmental literacy was assessed using a survey questionnaire.

The quantitative component employed a pre-experimental design, specifically a one-group post-test-only design. In this approach, a single group was studied after receiving the intervention, with no comparison group, and the treatment's success was determined solely based on the post-intervention outcomes. As defined by Campbell and Stanley (1966), the one-shot case study involves subjecting a single group to a treatment or intervention and then observing its effects.

For the qualitative component, thematic analysis was employed to systematically organize and interpret complex data to uncover themes reflecting the narratives within the dataset. Braun and Clarke (2006) emphasized that thematic analysis is a flexible tool for identifying, interpreting, and reporting patterns (themes) within data, applicable to diverse qualitative research contexts.

Participants

The researcher selected both Junior and Senior High School students from Lambayong National High School as respondents for this study. The participants were those enrolled during the 2024-2025 academic year, ranging in age from twelve to eighteen years. Students were chosen uniformly based on shared characteristics, ensuring a balanced representation of academic achievement levels—low, moderate, and high—across all groups.

For the qualitative component, a semi-structured interview was conducted with six (6) carefully selected participants. These included representatives from the winning classrooms and the presidents of key school organizations involved in the Zero-Waste Program's implementation: SSLG, YES-O, Red Cross Youth, and NDEP.

Creswell (2006) and Polkinghorne (2008), as cited by Accad and Accad (2016), suggested that 5-25 participants are sufficient for generalizations in qualitative research, supporting the adequacy of the selected sample size in this study.

Instrument

To collect quantitative data, the researcher administered a survey questionnaire. Part I of the survey, derived from Lualhati et al. (2018), assessed the extent of program execution in terms of student engagement that is consist of 10 items. Part II examined students' environmental literacy in terms of knowledge, attitude, and practices, using a questionnaire adapted from Nabor and Ortega (2022) consist of 18 items. Additionally, a supplementary 30-item survey was administered to determine the level of student achievement in environmental literacy.

For the qualitative part, thematic analysis by Braun & Clarke, (2006) was employed. This approach was based on strategic interventions proposed by the students to improve the implementation of the zero-waste initiative.

Procedure

The researcher first secured a letter of permission to conduct the study from the Office of the Dean of Graduate Studies. Subsequently, another letter was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Sultan Kudarat, requesting permission to use Lambayong National High School as the research site.

A separate letter was then sent to the principal of Lambayong National High School, seeking approval to involve students and teachers in the study. Since the Zero-Waste Program implementation began during the first grade of the 2024-2025 school year, students were asked to evaluate its implementation.

The researcher requested the cooperation of the selected students from grade 7-12 and a separated letter was also provided. The researcher set a date based on the availability of the respondents/ participants. Before administering the survey, the researcher oriented the students about the study. The researcher conducted the study both physically and online to ensure that learners provided accurate and appropriate responses. Finally, the data collected were consolidated and analyzed.

Results and Discussion

This section explained the result and analysis of the data gathered from the students' population of Lambayong National High School in school year 2024-2025 to assess the effectiveness of the Zero-Waste Program and students' environmental literacy to improve and promote environmental sustainability.

Table 1. *The Extent of Zero-Waste Program Implementation of the Student Participation*

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I segregate waste materials in our classroom	3.66	1.30	Very Effective
2. I use separate bins for recyclable and non-recyclable materials.	3.70	1.30	Very Effective
3. I reuse materials in our classroom instead of throwing them away.	3.44	1.26	Effective
4. I encourage my classmates to participate in the zero-waste program.	3.56	1.31	Very Effective
5. I use refillable water bottles or containers instead of single-use plastic bottles.	3.59	1.28	Very Effective
6. I bring my own reusable utensils and containers for snacks and meals.	3.61	1.27	Very Effective
7. I participate in zero-waste activities organized by our school.	3.72	1.30	Very Effective
8. We use compost organic waste in our classroom within school premises.	2.51	0.78	Effective
9. I participate in clean-up drives within the school compound.	3.51	1.35	Very Effective
10. I properly dispose of hazardous materials such as batteries and chemicals.	3.49	1.30	Effective
Grand Mean	3.58	0.96	Very Effective

Table 1 presents the extent of Zero-Waste Program implementation in terms of student participation. Among the items, item number 7, "I participate in zero-waste activities organized by our school," had the highest mean of 3.72 with a standard deviation of 1.30, interpreted as "Very Effective." This suggests that students actively participate in school-organized zero-waste activities, which is crucial for fostering a culture of sustainability within the school community.

This was followed by item number 2, "I use separate bins for recyclable and non-recyclable materials," with a mean of 3.70 and a standard deviation of 1.30, also interpreted as "Very Effective." This indicates that students consistently use separate bins, a practice essential for reducing contamination of recyclable materials.

Similarly, item number 1, "I segregate waste materials in our classroom," had a mean of 3.69 with a standard deviation of 1.30, interpreted as "Very Effective."

On the other hand, the lowest mean was observed in item number 3, "I reuse materials in our classroom instead of throwing them away," with a mean of 3.44 and a standard deviation of 1.26, interpreted as "Effective." This indicates that the zero-waste initiative encourages students to reuse materials more frequently. Followed by item number 10, "I properly dispose of hazardous materials such as batteries and chemicals," which had a mean of 3.49 with a standard deviation of 1.30, and still interpreted as "Effective."

The computed section mean was 3.58 with a standard deviation of 0.96, interpreted as "Very Effective." This implies that the zero-waste initiative reflects consistent participation in various components of the program and increases active participation of students at Lambayong National High School, demonstrating a strong commitment to sustainability and waste reduction.

In addition, the findings supported by the zero-waste initiative monthly evaluation. Several noticeable changes were observed since the implementation of the said initiative. The amount of solid waste is reduced in the classrooms, ground, and the school community. Also, students were little by little learned how to segregate waste accordingly. It is a manifestation that the said zero-waste initiative was really effective.

A similar study conducted by Abas et al. (2022) on university students' participation in the Waste-To-Wealth Program revealed lower levels of engagement. While some students participated in activities related to the program, most answered "No" to questions about their involvement in the university's waste-to-wealth initiatives. To address this, the study suggested interventions such as organizing field trips and outdoor activities to increase student interest and participation. Although similar in examining student participation, this study highlighted limited engagement in waste-to-wealth initiatives compared to the more consistent participation observed in the Zero-Waste Program at Lambayong National High School. The reason for the consistent students' participation on the zero-waste program initiatives is the rewards and incentives in a form of cash, cleaning materials, certificates, and a banner.

Table 2. *The Extent of Student's Environmental Literacy in Terms of Environmental Knowledge*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I am aware that our school is implementing a solid waste management program.	3.70	1.32	Very Knowledgeable
2. I am fully aware about the process of proper waste segregation.	3.72	1.28	Very Knowledgeable
3. I am aware where to throw the collected waste.	3.81	1.32	Very Knowledgeable
4. I am aware about the process of recycling.	3.67	1.29	Very Knowledgeable
5. I aware that garbage or waste is harmful to the environment.	3.66	1.31	Very Knowledgeable
6. I am aware that it is important to follow proper solid waste management to avoid possible health problems.	3.78	1.37	Very Knowledgeable
Section Mean	3.72	1.15	Very Knowledgeable

Table 2 revealed by respondents, the highest mean on the extent of environmental literacy awareness was item number 3 “I am aware where to throw the collected waste” with a mean of 3.81 at standard deviation of 1.32 interpreted as “Very Knowledgeable”. This statement indicates that students are well-informed about where to dispose of collected waste. Proper disposal practices help maintain cleanliness and reduce environmental pollution.

The second one was item number 6 “I am aware that it is important to follow proper solid waste management to avoid possible health problems.” with a mean of 3.78 at the standard deviation of 1.37 interpreted as “Very Knowledgeable”. This implies that the students understand the need of using proper solid waste management techniques to prevent possible health issues. This knowledge highlights the relationship between public health and environmental behavior.

Third one was item number 2, "I am fully aware about the process of proper waste segregation" with a mean of 3.72 at standard deviation of 1.28 interpreted as " Very Knowledgeable." This suggests that students are fully aware of the process of proper waste segregation. This knowledge is essential for effective waste management, ensuring that recyclable materials are properly separated from non-recyclables.

Then, the lowest mean value was item number 1 “. I am aware that garbage or waste is harmful to the environment.” with a mean of 3.66 at standard deviation of 1.31 interpreted as “Very Knowledgeable”, and item number “. I am aware about the process of recycling” with a mean of 3.67 at standard deviation of 1.29 interpreted as “Very Knowledgeable”.

The overall section mean of 3.72, accompanied by a standard deviation of 1.15. This underscores the necessity of providing individuals with the necessary information and understanding to make informed decisions and engage in environmental conservation efforts. This sustained awareness demonstrates that students have a fundamental comprehension of essential environmental ideas, which is vital for promoting sustainable behaviors.

These findings agreed with the study of Salva et al. (2020) that Filipino university students with higher levels of environmental knowledge were more likely to engage in environmentally friendly practices. Environmental awareness significantly influences waste disposal practices, underscoring the importance of enhancing environmental education. Developing sensible sustainability initiatives and creating municipal regulations that support environmental preservation depend on closing this knowledge gap (Balon, et al. 2021.)

Table 3. *The Extent of Student's Environmental Literacy in Terms of Environmental Attitude*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I believe that our school is practicing a very effective waste disposal method.	3.54	1.29	Highly Concerned
2. I believe that proper waste disposal in school is also the responsibility of the pupils	3.49	1.30	Neutral
3. I firmly believe that participating actively in our school's solid waste management program is a must.	3.66	1.24	Highly Concerned
4. I believe that collected waste or garbage must not be burned inside the school premises.	3.78	1.27	Highly Concerned
5. I believe that the teachers are trying to show us a good example of proper waste disposal.	3.87	1.35	Highly Concerned
6. I believe that the students in our school must cooperate in the proper disposal of garbage in our school.	3.74	1.30	Highly Concerned
Section Mean	3.67	1.10	Highly Concerned

Table 3 revealed the extent of student's environmental literacy in terms of environmental attitude, the highest mean was item number 5 “I believe that the teachers are trying to show us a good example of proper waste disposal” interpreted as “Highly Concerned”. This shows that, supported by a mean of 3.87 at standard deviation of 1.35, students highly believe that teachers are modelling responsible garbage disposal. Students' inclination to follow similar behaviors might be much influenced by their favorable view of professors' behavior.

Followed by item number 4 “I believe that collected waste or garbage must not be burned inside the school premises” with a mean of 3.78 at standard deviation of 1.27 interpreted as “Highly Concerned”. This shows that students are highly concerned with the environment and in support to the prohibition of burning of trashes within the school.

Then item number 6 "I believe that the students in our school must cooperate in the proper disposal of garbage in our school" with a mean of 3.74 at standard deviation of 1.30 translated "Highly Concerned." Students thus agree that appropriate trash management depends on peers working together. This mindset emphasizes the need of group work in reaching proper waste management.

Then, the lowest mean was item 2 "I believe that proper waste disposal in school is also the responsibility of the teachers" with a mean of 3.45 at standard deviation of 1.26 interpreted "Neutral." The mean score of 3.45 suggests that while some students may believe that teachers are responsible for the waste disposal in schools, others are uncertain of this situation.

The overall section mean of 3.67, with a standard deviation of 1.10, indicating that students shows a positive attitude towards environmental activities connected to trash management. The continuous agreement across numerous statements demonstrates a strong commitment to sustainability and a readiness to engage in responsible actions.

The students or the youth in general are in need to develop their attitude in dealing our environment, the way how generation care and sustained ecological needs. Additionally, active learning methods (Kardas & Uca, 2016) help students engage in their learning and encourage creativity and critical thinking. These methods are particularly efficient at increasing environmental awareness and encouraging favorable attitudes. This is supported by Mensa et. al (2021) that environmental attitude significantly impacts waste management practices.

Table 4. *The Extent of Student's Environmental Literacy in Terms of Environmental Practices*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I practice waste segregation inside our school premises by throwing garbage in appropriate containers.	3.57	1.29	Highly Practiced
2. I conduct waste recycling in our school.	2.93	1.05	Neutral
3. I practice waste recycling with my own school materials like paper, notebook and books.	3.31	1.30	Neutral
4. I am participating in our school's waste management activities.	3.63	1.25	Highly Practiced
5. I minimize the garbage/waste so I can help in the successful implementation our school's Zero-Waste Program.	3.66	1.24	Highly Practiced
6. I am following the rules imposed by the school about solid waste management.	3.82	1.27	Highly Practiced
Section Mean	3.59	0.97	Highly Practiced

Table 4 revealed the extent of student's environmental literacy in terms of environmental practices, the highest mean was item number 6 "I am following the rules imposed by the school about solid waste management" with a mean of 3.82 at standard deviation of 1.27 interpreted "Highly Practiced", this means students follow the rules imposed by the school regarding solid waste management. Maintaining a clean and sustainable school environment depends on following these guidelines.

Then, item number five "I minimize the garbage/waste so I can help in the successful implementation our school's Zero-Waste Program"; this means that students often take steps to minimize garbage and waste to support the successful implementation of the school's Zero-Waste Program, interpreted as "Highly Practiced," indicated by a mean score of 3.66 at standard deviation of 1.24. This proactive approach is key to reducing waste generation at the source.

Then, followed by the item number 4 "I am participating in our school's waste management activities" with a mean of 3.63 at standard deviation of 1.25 interpreted "Highly Practiced".

Further, the lowest mean was item number 2 "I conduct waste recycling in our school" with a mean score of 2.93 at standard deviation of 1.05 interpreted as "Neutral", this means that students sometimes engage in waste recycling within the school. This shows some degree of involvement, hence there is need for development to raise the frequency and regularity of recycling operations.

Then item number 3 "I practice waste recycling with my own school materials like paper, notebook and books with a mean of 3.31 at standard deviation of 1.30 translated as "Neutral."

With a standard deviation of 0.97, the total section mean of 3.59 shows that students, by their behavior inside the institution, underscores a higher level of sustainable practices in many wastes management.

Effective waste management practices help to lower pollution of land, water, and air. Mensah et al. (2021) claim that recycling and waste management mostly help the environment. Moreover, recycling can help to save energy and lower carbon emissions related with the manufacture of new products. In public elementary schools, Ferrer and Sarol (2018) assessed waste segregation, composting, and recycling programs, therefore stressing the need of community involvement and education and emphasizing the requirement of infrastructure and awareness-building campaigns, Montecillo and Lu (2016) found obstacles and effective waste management techniques for educational institutions. Gaspay et al. (2019) underlined how student participation helps to support environmentally friendly educational policies.

Furthermore, very important for the preservation of the ecology are recycling and waste control. Recycling paper, plastic, and metal reduces the demand for new raw materials, therefore supporting mining, deforestation, and other harmful projects.

Table 5. *The Level Of Student’s Achievement On Their Environmental Literacy*

<i>Students’ Achievement Scores</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>% distribution</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1-6	3	0.73	VLEL
7-12	86	20.98	LEL
13-18	159	38.78	AEL
19-24	139	33.90	AAEL
25-30	23	5.61	VHEL

*VLEL- Very Low Environmental Literacy, LEL- Very Low Environmental Literacy, AEL- Average Environmental Literacy
AAEL- Above Average Environmental Literacy, VHEL- Very High Environmental Literacy*

Table 5 revealed the level of student’s achievement test score on their environmental literacy, showed that the highest mean percentage score (MPS) was bracket 13-18 score with the frequency of 156 or thirty eight point seventy eight (38.78%) described “Average Environmental Literacy”, then followed by the bracket 19-24 score with the frequency of 139 or thirty three point ninety percent (33.90%) described “ Above Average Environmental Literacy”, then third one was bracket 7-12 with a frequency of eighty six (86) or twenty point ninety eighth percent (20.98%). The lowest mean percentage score was bracket 1-6 with a frequency of 3 or 0.73.

This implies that students in Lambayong National High School at the average level in terms of the environmental literacy. The zero-waste initiative only highlights on the actual segregation of waste by encouraging students to practice the 3R’s, conducting cleaning up drives, and participating in the zero-waste activities. There’s no enough activity that involves providing the students the concept of solid waste management.

In order to produce responsible and ecologically conscious people equipped to solve environmental problems, environmental education must be incorporated into college courses, Palileo-Villanueva et al. (2018). This is supported by Green et. al (2022) stating that environmental education should be an important priority and must be incorporated in the academic curriculum and student participation helps to support environmentally friendly activities in educational institutions Gaspay et al. (2019).

Table 6. *Significant Influence Between Students’ Participation on Zero-Waste Program Implementation and the Level of their Achievement on Environmental Literacy (n=409)*

	<i>B</i>	<i>S.E</i>	<i>β</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p-value</i>
(Constant)	14.246	.883		16.126	.000
Student Participation	.766	.245	.153	3.127	.002*

F (1,407) = 9.780, p = .002b, R = .153a, R2 = .023, ΔR2 = .021

In table 6, The simple linear regression analysis results show that there is a strong association between students' participation in the Zero-Waste Program Implementation and their degree of environmental literacy. The model summary shows a R value of 0.153, indicating a weak positive relationship between the level of student participation and environmental literacy outcomes. The coefficient of determination (R2) is 0.023, indicating that student participation in zero-waste projects accounts for approximately 2.3% of the variance in environmental literacy achievement. While the effect magnitude is low, it is statistically significant.

The ANOVA table shows an F-value of 9.780 and a p-value of 0.002, indicating that the regression model is statistically significant. This suggests that student engagement in the Zero-Waste Program has a considerable impact on predicting their environmental literacy levels. The coefficients table reveals an standardized coefficient of 0.766 for student engagement, with a t-value of 3.127 and a p-value of 0.002. This means that for every unit increase in involvement, there is a 0.766 unit gain in environmental literacy attainment, assuming all other parameters remain constant.

These findings highlight the impact of zero-waste initiative on the level of environmental literacy achievement with low effect but still statistically significant. Environmental literacy is complex which includes, knowledge, attitudes, and behavior towards the environment as highlighted by McBride et. al (2023). Monroe et al. (2019) emphasized that experiential learning opportunities, such as participation in zero-waste projects, can dramatically increase environmental literacy by giving students realistic scenarios in which to apply theoretical knowledge. This hands-on experience encourages critical thinking and prepares students to be environmentally responsible citizens. Hungerford and Volk (2000) added that environmental education encourages active participation increases students' environmental knowledge and responsibility.

Moreover, the modest effect size suggests that while participation is important, it should be complemented with other educational strategies. Incorporating comprehensive environmental education programs that address cognitive, affective, and behavioral components may yield more substantial improvements in environmental literacy (Erhabor & Don, 2020). To have successful implementation of the program, educators should be aware of additional elements that influence environmental literacy, such as socioeconomic status, access to natural surroundings, and prior knowledge. Tailoring programs to these criteria can result in more inclusive and effective educational experiences.

In table 7, the MANOVA analysis demonstrates the positive impact of student participation in zero-waste programs on environmental education. Despite the small effect size, the statistically significant relationship suggests that such engagement is an important component of environmental education. Educators can improve students' environmental literacy by encouraging active participation in sustainability efforts, which will help them develop into environmentally conscientious persons.

Table 7. *The Extent of Student’s Participation in Sustainability Efforts Which Help them Develop into Environmentally Conscientious Persons (MANOVA) Result*

	Effect	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.954	2510.737b	3.000	366.000	.000	.954
	Wilks' Lambda	.046	2510.737b	3.000	366.000	.000	.954
	Hotelling's Trace	20.580	2510.737b	3.000	366.000	.000	.954
	Roy's Largest Root	20.580	2510.737b	3.000	366.000	.000	.954
MEANSP	Pillai's Trace	.957	4.307	120.000	1104.000	.000	.319
	Wilks' Lambda	.194	6.658	120.000	1097.395	.000	.421
	Hotelling's Trace	3.407	10.353	120.000	1094.000	.000	.532
	Roy's Largest Root	3.189	29.339c	40.000	368.000	.000	.761

a. Design: Intercept + MEANSP

b. Exact statistic

c. The statistic is an upper bound on F that yields a lower bound on the significance level.

Participation in the Zero-Waste initiative (MEANSP) significantly improves students' environmental literacy, according to multivariate tests (Pillai's Trace, Wilks' Lambda, Hotelling's Trace, and Roy's Largest Root, <0.001). Pillai's Trace (=4.307,=0.000) shows a significant multivariate effect, implying that participation affects the collective components of environmental literacy (knowledge, attitudes, and practices). With effect values from 0.319 to 0.761 depending on the statistic, partial Eta Squared values indicate a moderate to strong relationship. This suggests that program participation explains a lot of environmental literacy variation.

Based on the findings, participation in the Zero-Waste Program allows students to actively engage improving their understanding of environmental issues. These findings show that environmental literacy is more than just learning facts; it is also about developing beliefs and behaviors that are necessary for dealing with environmental issues. These findings support prior research emphasizing environmental literacy through active participation. Monroe et al. (2019) argues that experiential learning, such as participation in environmental programs, not only improves cognitive comprehension but also builds positive attitudes and promotes responsible environmental practices. Similarly, Hungerford and Volk (1990) emphasize the significance of environmental education programs that combine behavioral and participatory techniques to produce meaningful learning and long-term behavior change.

Table 8. *The Result of Tests of Between-Subjects Effects of the Lambayong National High School Students’ Respondent*

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	Environmental Knowledge	371.155a	40	9.279	20.268	.000	.688
	Environmental Attitude	340.568b	40	8.514	20.731	.000	.693
	Environmental Practices	270.541c	40	6.764	21.430	.000	.700
Intercept	Environmental Knowledge	2172.080	1	2172.080	4744.461	.000	.928
	Environmental Attitude	2099.141	1	2099.141	5111.159	.000	.933
	Environmental Practices	1873.575	1	1873.575	5936.419	.000	.942
MEANSP	Environmental Knowledge	371.155	40	9.279	20.268	.000	.688
	Environmental Attitude	340.568	40	8.514	20.731	.000	.693
	Environmental Practices	270.541	40	6.764	21.430	.000	.700
Error	Environmental Knowledge	168.476	368	.458			
	Environmental Attitude	151.137	368	.411			
	Environmental Practices	116.143	368	.316			
Total	Environmental Knowledge	6213.333	409				
	Environmental Attitude	6010.056	409				
	Environmental Practices	5360.833	409				
Corrected Total	Environmental Knowledge	539.631	408				
	Environmental Attitude	491.705	408				
	Environmental Practices	386.685	408				

a. R Squared = .688 (Adjusted R Squared = .654)

b. R Squared = .693 (Adjusted R Squared = .659)

c. R Squared = .700 (Adjusted R Squared = .667)

In table 8, The results of the between-subjects effects tests show that student involvement in the Zero-Waste Program has a considerable impact on their environmental literacy, particularly in terms of knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. The study found great statistical significance (p<0.001) and huge effect sizes, highlighting the importance of engagement in influencing students' environmental literacy. The partial eta squared ($\eta^2=0.688$) indicates that participation in the program accounts for roughly 68.8% of the variation in students' grasp of environmental concepts. The impact size ($\eta^2=0.693$) indicates that student participation influences 69.3% of the variance in their perception and feelings about environmental issues. Finally, the greatest impact is seen for environmental activities, where 70.0% of the variance ($\eta^2 =0.700$) in students' environmentally responsible behaviors can be explained by their engagement in the program.

These findings highlight the transformative potential of participatory environmental programs for promoting comprehensive environmental literacy. Active participation in sustainability projects such as the Zero-Waste Program allows students to get experiential learning opportunities that go beyond theoretical understanding. This hands-on experience not only improves students understanding of environmental issues, but it also fosters positive attitudes and encourages actionable, responsible environmental

behaviors. This is consistent with Monroe et al. (2019), who argue that participatory environmental education improves both cognitive and behavioral results. Additionally, Abdel-Shafy and Mansour (2018) argue that behavior-focused environmental education is critical for establishing long-term pro-environmental actions among students.

The consequences of these findings are significant for educators and program designers. For educators, it emphasizes the importance of incorporating participatory environmental projects within the curriculum in order to optimize their impact on student environmental literacy. Program designers can improve the success of such efforts by including real-world, hands-on activities that increase student engagement and learning. Furthermore, future research might investigate the various effects of different degrees of participation and identify specific program components that provide the greatest advantages.

Presentation Of Qualitative Findings

Strategic Intervention on School Community

Pertinent themes were identified based on suggested Strategic Intervention on School Community. Through a series of laborious and stringent procedures in data analysis and interpretation and five (5) relevant themes were articulated.

Relevant Theme 1: Fostering a Culture of Sustainability

The participants revealed that fostering a culture of sustainability had big contribution to address waste issues in the school. Sustainability of the school program on zero-waste has vital role in preventing health problem of the learners. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Zero Waste Program helps the school to maintain the cleanliness around the campus, especially in the classrooms.” in the lines Environmentalist #1 19, and 20.

“I think the school community must fully adopt sustainable waste management practices to strengthen awareness, campaigns and implement a comprehensive waste segregation system”. in the lines Environmentalist #3 114 115, and 116.

“Para sa akin, upang mas lalong mapabuti ang zero-waste initiative sa paaralan ay dapat meron tayo isang kultura na tinatawag na pagpapanatili. (For me, to further improve the zero-waste initiative in the school community, it's essential to cultivate a culture of sustainability.)” in the lines Environmentalist #4 157, 158, 162, and 163.

“Regularly host community events like clean-up drives and sustainability fairs to keep everyone engaged.” in the lines Environmentalist #5 216, and 217.

“Promote a zero-waste culture by integrating sustainability into school activities and events. Establish a Green Team, consisting of teachers, students, and parents, to lead waste management initiatives. Hold regular clean-up drives, recycling workshops, and competitions to keep everyone engaged and motivated.” in the lines Environmentalist #6 256, 257, 258, 259, and 260.

Additionally, fostering a culture of sustainability entails building an environment in which sustainable activities are integrated into daily life and valued by the community. Related study on environmental leadership has lately emerged as a critical component in identifying sustainable development methods that prioritize environmental concerns. Sustainability, as observed by Dager and Jordan (2019), needs purposeful planning and execution rather than occurring naturally. The concept is especially relevant in the context of environmental governance and waste management in Jordan, where various strategies and frameworks have been developed to promote sustainable practices. This theme focuses on instilling sustainable values in the school community through workshops, ambassador programs, and continuous education. Participants emphasized the necessity of appointing zero-waste champions and hosting frequent knowledge-sharing workshops.

Sustainable waste management aims to keep hazardous trash out of the environment while simultaneously increasing resource recovery through recycling and other methods. However, obtaining 100% waste eradication remains a challenge, with governments looking into innovative waste management solutions (Kuehle-Weidemeier et al., 2019). Malletz et al. (2019) contend that policies such as funding mandates, incinerator retirement, organic material surcharges, extended producer responsibility, and single-use plastic bans are crucial for decreasing waste and fostering sustainable practices.

Further, Gaspay et al. (2019) emphasized the need of engaging students in sustainability projects within educational settings. Schools that foster an environment in which students can actively participate in and lead sustainability initiatives educate future generations about environmental issues while also enabling them to be proactive stewards of the land. Furthermore, the literature supports this by proving the importance of educational programs in promoting pro-environmental behavior (Barr et al., 2019). These efforts encourage social responsibility, making sustainable habits the norm in the community. The findings indicate that schools should integrate sustainability education into their daily operations, making it an intrinsic part of their culture.

Thus, joint efforts between government agencies and the community are vitally required to achieve the goals of sustainable waste management. Collaboration in waste management involves both adhering to government policies and engaging in open dialogue to find shared solutions (Dagilienė et al., 2021).

Relevant Theme 2: Developing Zero-Waste Infrastructure

The participants on this theme focuses on creating amenities such as color-coded bins, composting sites, and recycling stations. Such infrastructure promotes proper garbage management. These solutions ensure systematic trash segregation and encourage adherence to zero-waste ideals. Schools must prioritize infrastructure improvements in order to effectively institutionalize waste management procedures. These are the common projects aside from the educational campaign implemented in the school or institution to achieve zero-waste. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Building a sustainable school environment supportive of zero-waste goals, like installing clearly labeled, color-coded bins around the campus for different types of waste to promote proper segregation and setting up a composting area for biodegradable waste to be used in the school garden, creating a sustainable loop.” in the lines Environmentalist #1 20, 21, 22, 23, 24 and 25.

“Letting up recycling stations and composting bins around the campus with clear instructions.” in the lines Environmentalist #2 70, and 71.

Similar study on developing zero-waste infrastructure is a multidimensional process that requires strategic planning, community engagement, and major investment. Exemplary cases such as San Francisco show that good legislation and community involvement may drastically reduce trash generation and promote sustainable practices. Initiatives led by organizations such as the UNDP demonstrate the potential for international cooperation in achieving these goals. As cities around the world strive for zero waste, sharing best practices and insights will be critical to promote a sustainable future. EPA Gov. (2022).

Relevant Theme 3: Engaging the Community

Another crucial issue is community engagement revealed by the participants which includes initiatives like clean-up campaigns, collaborations with local businesses, and sustainability exhibitions. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Organize cleanup drives that involves students, teachers, and community members and partnership with local government units.” in the lines Environmentalist #1 28, 29, and 30.

“Establishing partnerships with local businesses for the sustainable supply of school materials.” in the Environmentalist #2 72, 73, and 74.

“Encouraging active participation from teachers, staff and parents in the zero-waste activities such as waste audits and recycling programs.” in the lines Environmentalist #3 116, 117, and 118.

“Establish a Green Team, consisting of teachers, students, and parents, to lead waste management initiatives. Hold regular clean-up drives, recycling workshops, and competitions to keep everyone engaged and motivated.” in the lines Environmentalist #6 257, 258, 259, and 260.

In the school, the above activities always implemented in school campus and outside. The related study Involving stakeholders not only broadens the scope of zero-waste initiatives, but also increases collective action. Wardhani (2019) states that the efficiency of waste management plans is heavily dependent on the active participation of all stakeholders (Kuang & Lin, 2021; Kisset al., 2022). Ferrer and Sarol (2018) shown that, while many schools have implemented garbage segregation and recycling programs, their performance is often dependent on ongoing instruction and community support. Furthermore, it was shown that institutions with complete waste management instructional systems had much greater levels of student engagement and program effectiveness.

Successful waste management initiatives in schools require a dual focus on community engagement and educational initiatives, as Austin (2013) emphasized the importance of collaboration among citizens, corporations, educational institutions, governmental bodies, and manufacturers for effective waste management outcomes. Furthermore, public perceptions of waste management influence community engagement, with education and outreach playing a significant role in influencing attitudes and behaviors (Kumar et al., 2016). A robust social network promotes garbage segregation behavior (Ling et al., 2021).

Schools may promote a more sustainable approach to waste management by building an informed community that actively participates in these programs. McKenzie-Mohr (2020) discovered that community-based interventions are very effective at influencing behavior through social norms and reciprocal accountability. As a result, schools may leverage community support to develop impact and sustainable programs.

Relevant Theme 4: Leadership and Governance

Participants revealed that leadership and governance had an important role in governing and guiding students leader in addressing waste problem in the school. Further, related study on leadership and their function according to the proper organizational structure. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Establish an eco-committee consisting of teachers, students and parents to lead and oversee ongoing Zero Waste initiatives.” in the lines Environmentalist #5 214, 215, and 216.

“Establish a Green Team, consisting of teachers, students, and parents, to lead waste management initiatives.” in the lines Environmentalist #6 257, and 258.

Leadership structures, such as eco-committees and green teams, give strategic guidance for zero-waste initiatives. The theme emphasizes the need of governance in program sustainability. Stern et al. (2021) argue that governance frameworks are crucial for resource management and compliance. Schools that establish clear leadership roles can assure responsibility and continual progress in waste management.

The solid waste management program will collapse due to a lack of resources. As a result, community members will be unsatisfied (Lad, Chauhan, and Gole, 2020). Leadership and effective governance are critical for active involvement by students and teachers, as well as the long-term viability of the zero-waste initiative. Al-Katib et al. (2020) emphasized that effective solid waste management requires technical, political, legal, socio-cultural, environmental, and economic factors, as well as readily available resources.

The success of zero-waste projects is dependent on leaders' capacity to inspire, guide, and mobilize resources, as well as strong governance structures that ensure compliance, accountability, and continual improvement. Effective leadership is one approach to improving certain habits, such as zero-waste campaigns. A transformational leader not only motivates followers to complete tasks, but also encourages them to grow personally and exceed expectations. As a result, community members' engagement in solid waste management programs is determined by the activities of their leaders or authority (San Juan, 2019).

Relevant Theme 5: Incentivizing Waste Reduction

The participants also revealed that given awards and recognition to the students leader, and students motivates much learners to cooperate in the implemented program. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Also, implementing a reward system for departments of our organization with the least waste production.” in the lines Environmentalist #2 71 and 72.

“Isulong ang mga patakaran na sumusuporta sa mga zero-waste programs, tulad ng pagbibigay ng incentives para sa pagbawas ng basura at pagpapatupad ng mga programang composting. (In relation to the government, it's important to strengthen partnerships with local governments to secure funding and resources. Advocate for policies that support zero-waste programs, such as providing incentives for waste reduction and implementing composting programs.)” in the lines Environmentalist #4 170, 171, 172, 173, 174, 175, and 176.

Accordingly, providing awards and recognition for departments or people displaying great performance in waste reduction encourages involvement, and as agreed with (Kirakozian, 2016), programs that offer incentives are more likely to attract participants.

Motivation is critical to the success of zero waste project competitions because it fosters involvement, builds community, provides information, and establishes clear goals. Organizations and communities can boost their efforts to achieve sustainable waste management practices by capitalizing on these motivators.

Deci and Ryan (2020) found that positive reinforcement increases intrinsic motivation, which is necessary for long-term behavioral change. Similarly, Aini et al. (2022) and Tadesse (2019) stated that intrinsic motivation and personal commitments are the key motivators. Furthermore, economic motivation can indirectly influence behavior by giving incentives and disincentives through pricing, which is more efficient and adaptive than command-and-control systems (Cohen, 2019).

The South African trash Act 59 of 2008 authorizes the Ministers of Environmental Affairs and Finance to provide incentives and disincentives for changing trash generation and management methods (Godfrey and Oelofse, 2017). Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) regulations can significantly minimize the environmental effect of products by encouraging manufacturers to reduce packaging and promote recyclability. On the other hand, Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) policies have the ability to reduce waste by holding producers accountable for their products throughout their entire lifecycle (Sakano, 2015).

The themes demonstrate that creating a zero-waste culture necessitates a holistic approach that includes infrastructure, community participation, leadership, and individual dedication. Schools serve as microcosms of larger societal change, making them excellent beginning sites for zero-waste efforts. Policies should combine educational strategies, stakeholder participation, and government partnership to provide a comprehensive framework for sustainable behaviors. To increase engagement, schools should create equal incentive structures that encourage healthy competition.

Strategic Intervention on Government

Pertinent themes were identified based on suggested Strategic Intervention on Government. Through a series of laborious and stringent procedures in data analysis and interpretation and five (5) relevant themes were articulated.

Relevant Theme 1: Securing Government Support

Majority of the participants suggest that securing government support is very important to sustain the program implemented to achieved zero-waste in the school. It means the success of the program depend on the level of government support. These sentiments are reflected

in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Securing a government support for expanding zero-waste efforts within the school through coordinating with the government to organize cleanup drives that involves students, teachers, and community members and partnership with local government units or also known as the LGUs to facilitate collection and provide resources for composting and recycling efforts.” in the lines Environmentalist #1 27, 28, 29, 30, and 31.

“I think we must request government support for waste segregation infrastructure and provide educational materials in collaboration with local government units to establish regular waste collection and recycling services.” in the lines Environmentalist #2 77, 78, 79, and 80.

Waste management cannot be accomplished without the government's support, which is critical for developing policy, building infrastructure, and involving the community. This core notion emphasizes the importance of public support for zero-waste projects, including financial backing, rigorous adherence to environmental standards, and the availability of necessary resources. Infrastructure, curriculum development, and continued activities all highlighted the importance of government assistance. In the context of resource management, research emphasizes the importance of strong institutional support for collaborative action. When the government supports zero-waste programs in schools and neighborhoods, they have a much better chance of succeeding.

This means that schools should actively seek grants, subsidies, and technical support from government agencies to strengthen their programs, because governments can support the ethical handling of municipal garbage by implementing specific policies (Valizadeh, Aghdamigargari, et al., 2021; Valizadeh, Aickelin, et al., 2021; Valizadeh, Mozafari, et al., 2021; Valizadeh, Sayed Alizadeh, et al., 2021), and policymakers must prioritize funding allocations for educational institution.

Furthermore, all governments are aiming toward sustainable development on all fronts—economic, environmental, and social (Tseng et al., 2018), and sustainability integration has gained a lot of attention recently. According to Abdel-Basset et al. (2020), municipal waste collection, like other activities, considers the economic and financial outcomes, as well as the social and environmental consequences, in order to ensure sustainability.

Further, in the context of trash management, collaboration between government agencies and the community is vitally required to achieve the goals of sustainable waste management. The government acts as a policy regulator, legislator, and facility supplier, while the community serves as the primary implementer of these policies on the ground. In addition, the community helps to provide facilities. Jotaworn et al. (2021) emphasize in their study that waste management solutions will not work optimally unless both sides collaborate significantly.

As a result, the current environmental challenges will become more complex and difficult to address. Even if the government has created TPS facilities and conducted awareness campaigns, the difficulties will persist if the general people continue to ignore the significance of proper trash sorting or littering without concern for the consequences of their actions. In a same line, community efforts such as the school's zero-waste campaign, which aim to manage garbage independently, require government assistance in the form of legislation and adequate infrastructure (Astheria & Herdiansyah, 2022). Thus, the government's commitment to guaranteeing the continuity and durability of such programs is required for them to be successful (Masuda et al., 2022).

Relevant Theme 2: Collaboration with Local Government Units (LGUs)

Participants underscored the importance of cooperating with local governments (LGUs) to enhance garbage segregation, collection, and recycling. Providing the resources required to promote zero-waste habits and organizing community-wide initiatives. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Community members and partnership with local government units or also known as the LGUs to facilitate collection and provide resources for composting and recycling efforts.” in the lines Environmentalist #1 29, 30, and 31.

“For me, having a strong collaboration between local government and schools to support zero-waste initiative is a must. I think we must request government support for waste segregation infrastructure and provide educational materials in collaboration with local government units to establish regular waste collection and recycling services.” in the lines Environmentalist #2 76, 77, 78, 79, and 80.

“For the government, collaborating with local government units to secure support for infrastructure such as recycling centers and to enforce stricter regulation on waste management within schools. Seek assistance for funding sustainable school projects because I believe that having a stronger government support enforcing environmental laws and providing resources for school programs like this will lead to success.” in the lines Environmentalist #3 120, 121, 123, 124, and 125.

“Sa ugnayan sa pamahalaan, kailangan palakasin ang mga pakikipagtulungan sa mga lokal na pamahalaan upang makakuha ng pondo at mga resources. Isulong ang mga patakaran na sumusuporta sa mga zero-waste programs, tulad ng pagbibigay ng incentives para sa pagbawas ng basura at pagpapatupad ng mga programang composting. (In relation to the government, it's important to strengthen partnerships with local governments to secure funding and resources. Advocate for policies that support zero-waste programs, such as providing incentives for waste reduction and implementing composting programs)” in the lines Environmentalist #4 168, 169, 170, 171, 172, 173, 174, 175, and 176.

“For the government, strengthening collaboration with the local government is the best thing to do.” in the lines Environmentalist #5 219 and 220.

“Partner with local government units to secure funding and support for waste management programs.” in the lines Environmentalist #5 262, and 263.

Collaboration between institutions and local authorities ensures better compliance and resource optimization, and this is similar to (Austin, 2023), revealed that collaboration among citizens, companies, governments, and manufacturers is essential for effective waste management efforts, and agreed with Allison Creeger (2019), revealing that a large portion of dissatisfied citizens desired more active leadership/collaboration from local government to improve waste management.

Further, the rubbish in the school is picked up and collected on a daily basis by the Lambayong Local Government Unit's garbage truck. Whether we like it or not, the customer takes the first step in trash management, and there is no such thing as "throwing away" your trash because it will always be on the ground, in a landfill, or in the air due to incineration, according to Hoonweg (2022). Thus, it is believed that once people understand this and adjust their attitudes, the waste stream will slow down and put less pressure on the other aspects of waste management. Collection is usually the following stage, and it varies by area. Self-delivered, curbside or house-to-house pickup, communal bins, and hired services are available. Government intervention, including mandates and control procedures, is necessary to ensure compliance and widespread participation in waste management programs.

Relevant Theme 3: Developing Waste Management Infrastructure

The participants revealed that developing waste management infrastructure such as the proper disposal and machinery contributed much in achieving zero-waste in the school and community in general. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Building a sustainable school environment supportive of zero-waste goals, like installing clearly labeled, color-coded bins around the campus for different types of waste to promote proper segregation and setting up a composting area for biodegradable waste to be used in the school garden, creating a sustainable loop.” in the lines Environmentalist #1 20, 21, 22, 23, 24 and 25.

“Letting up recycling stations and composting bins around the campus with clear instructions.” in the lines Environmentalist #2 70, and 71.

Another major topic was the creation of recycling centers, composting spaces, and waste segregation systems. Participants highlighted infrastructure as a critical component of effective zero-waste projects. McKenzie-Mohr (2021) found that accessible and user-friendly infrastructure greatly increases participation in pro-environmental practices. Governments must prioritize investments in waste management infrastructure, particularly in educational facilities. Policies should require baseline infrastructure standards for schools and encourage compliance.

Relevant Theme 4: Policy Advocacy and Incentives

Participants stressed the need of advocating for legislation that support zero-waste practices, such as enforcing waste segregation and offering incentives to schools that meet zero-waste targets. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Also, implementing a reward system for departments of our organization with the least waste production.” in the lines Environmentalist #2 71 and 72.

“Isulong ang mga patakaran na sumusuporta sa mga zero-waste programs, tulad ng pagbibigay ng incentives para sa pagbawas ng basura at pagpapatupad ng mga programang composting. (In relation to the government, it's important to strengthen partnerships with local governments to secure funding and resources. Advocate for policies that support zero-waste programs, such as providing incentives for waste reduction and implementing composting programs.)” in the lines Environmentalist #4 170, 171, 172, 173, 174, 175, and 176.

“Push for local policies that mandate waste segregation and recycling in schools and advocating for incentives for schools that achieve Zero Waste goals.” in the lines Environmentalist #5 221, 222, and 223.

“Advocate for policies that encourage waste reduction and recycling in schools, such as grants for eco-friendly projects or awards for schools that achieve zero-waste goals.” in the lines Environmentalist #6 263, 264, and 265.

According to Deci and Ryan (2020) underline the importance of positive reinforcement and policy-driven incentives in promoting sustainable behavior. Schools and environmentalists could advocate for regulations that require waste management techniques and provide financial or reputational incentives for meeting sustainability targets.

Relevant Theme 5: Educational and Training Programs

The participants agreed and revealed that educational training and program is the top priority to the learners to achieved zero-waste because, they believed that environmental literate students contributed to sustained zero-waste program implementation. These

sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Provide educational materials in collaboration with local government units to establish regular waste collection and recycling services.” in the lines Environmentalist #2 78, 79 and 80.

“Collaborate with government agencies to provide training and resources for effective waste management.” in the lines Environmentalist #6 265, and 266.

This theme focuses on delivering educational resources and training programs in partnership with government entities. Participants proposed programs and tools to help instructors, staff, and students gain knowledge and skills for good waste management. Barr et al. (2021) argue that education is a critical driver in changing attitudes toward sustainability. Governments should contribute money to instructional initiatives aimed at students, teachers, and community members training programs must contain practical, hands-on components to guarantee that knowledge is effectively implemented.

Strategic government interventions are critical to the success of zero-waste efforts. Schools necessitate strong government involvement, from finance and infrastructure development to policy campaigning and education. Schools that collaborate with LGUs can improve resource availability and policy compliance. Furthermore, governments can encourage involvement by offering targeted incentives and recognition programs, ensuring that zero-waste practices are integrated into educational and community institutions.

Strategic Intervention on Students

Pertinent themes were identified based on Suggested Strategic Intervention on Students. Through a series of laborious and stringent procedures in data analysis and interpretation and five (5) relevant themes were articulated.

Relevant Theme 1: Student Empowerment and Leadership

Participants revealed that in school, student body organization had major function to lead students, and that was the reason student empowerment and leadership was contributing factors in achieving zero-waste program. This empowerment through seminar, training. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“For me, cultivating environmental responsibility and zero-waste habits in students like eco-leadership programs where we can empower student leaders to spread head zero-waste campaigns, cleanup drives, and recycling projects, promoting a student-led culture of environmental stewardship.” in the lines Environmentalist #1 34, 35, 36, and 37.

“Encouraging student-led eco clubs that spearhead projects such as tree planting, recycling drives, or waste audits.” in the lines Environmentalist #2 84, 85.

This theme promotes student-led projects like eco-clubs, leadership programs, and zero-waste campaigns. Participants emphasized the need of empowering student leaders to plan and lead zero-waste initiatives such as recycling drives and composting programs. Bandura's (1977) social learning theory supports the premise that students who take up leadership roles model long-term behaviors for their peers, encouraging group action. Schools can develop opportunities for students to take on leadership positions, instilling a sense of ownership and responsibility in zero-waste projects.

A similar study by Biggar et al. (2015) found that a group of fifth-grade students who were empowered through leadership outperformed students who were not empowered in both English and arithmetic. Furthermore, it was revealed that students who have been empowered through leadership are more confident and achieve higher levels of academic accomplishment than students who have not. Unlike previous studies on student empowerment, this study focuses on students who have advanced into leadership roles rather than students from schools that encourage all students to be leaders.

Furthermore, student servant leadership programs have been investigated at institutions. Christian institutions include colleges, private Christian high schools, and churches. According to Baker (2015), the United States' public education system has failed to prepare students to be servant leaders. kids who enroll in faith-based schools and take more Religious Education Examination subjects perform better on academic achievement assessments than kids who do not attend faith-based schools. Thus, servant leadership is a relatively new leadership theory with limited study (Beck, 2014).

Relevant Theme 2: Curriculum Integration of Zero-Waste Principles

Participants proposed incorporating zero-waste teaching into a variety of courses, including science and social studies, to increase awareness of environmental challenges. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Integrating zero-waste education into curriculum with practical lessons and reducing, reusing, and recycling.” in the lines Environmentalist #2 82 and 83.

“Incorporating Zero Waste principles into the curriculum.” in the line Environmentalist #5 255.

This is consistent with Barr et al. (2011), who suggest that including sustainability into educational curricula increases environmental knowledge and promotes long-term behavior change. Schools must create curricula that contain both theoretical and practical waste

management teachings, allowing students to use classroom information in real-world situations.

Relevant Theme 3: Hands-On Learning and Activities

Participants said that, this theme emphasizes engaging students in hands-on activities such as workshops, competitions, and projects like ecobrick-making, tree planting, and campus cleanups. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Encouraging student-led initiatives like waste reduction competitions, eco-brick projects and campus cleanups.” in the lines Environmentalist #3 129 and 130.

“Para sa mga mag-aaral, sa tingin ko, kailangan magpatupad ng mga hands-on na workshop at kompetisyon tungkol sa zero-waste initiative ng school kailangan talaga. (For students, implementing hands-on workshops and competitions about the school's zero-waste initiative is necessary.)” in the lines Environmentalist #4 178, 179, 180, 181, 182, and 183.

“For me, Educate students on the importance of waste management through interactive lessons and projects.” in the lines Environmentalist #6 268, and 269.

Related study about sustainability by action or hands-on experiences help students better comprehend and adhere to sustainable practices Kolb, 2000). These exercises make learning more enjoyable and participatory. Schools should hold regular events and activities that allow students to apply their knowledge in practical ways, creating greater involvement with sustainability goals.

Relevant Theme 4: Incentives and Recognition

The participants said that reward systems and recognition were proposed as motivators for active student participation in zero-waste projects. In the school, administrator and school principal itself exercise the recognition and awarding of certificates to the outstanding students and good leader to motivate them with regards to the school program implemented. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Also, implementing a reward system for departments of our organization with the least waste production.” in the lines Environmentalist #2 71 and 72.

“Isulong ang mga patakaran na sumusuporta sa mga zero-waste programs, tulad ng pagbibigay ng incentives para sa pagbawas ng basura at pagpapatupad ng mga programang composting. (In relation to the government, it's important to strengthen partnerships with local governments to secure funding and resources. Advocate for policies that support zero-waste programs, such as providing incentives for waste reduction and implementing composting programs.) In the lines Environmentalist #4 170, 171, 172, 173, 174, 175, and 176.

“Implementing a reward system for those who demonstrate sustainable practices.” in the lines Environmentalist #6 270 and 271.

According to Deci and Ryan (2000), external rewards can supplement intrinsic motivation, boosting long-term participation in pro-environmental actions. Schools can offer certificates, eco-awards, or public recognition to pupils who exhibit a strong dedication to zero-waste activities.

Relevant Theme 5: Active Engagement in Sustainability Initiatives

Participants stressed the value of student-led initiatives such as organizing recycling drives, developing composting programs, and performing trash audits. These projects enable students to make direct contributions to the school's zero-waste goals. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Encouraging student-led eco clubs that spearhead projects such as tree planting, recycling drives, or waste audits.” in lines Environmentalist #2 83 and 84.

“Create opportunities for students to lead waste management initiatives, such as starting a composting program or organizing a recycling drive.” in the lines Environmentalist #6 271, 272, and 273.

According to McKenzie-Mohr (2021) emphasizes that student-led community-based activities promote accountability and shared purpose. Schools should provide tools and coaching to assist student-led sustainability projects, allowing students to play an active role in establishing a zero-waste culture.

Strategic interventions aimed at students emphasize the role of leadership, education, and incentives in developing a culture of sustainability. Schools may foster an environmentally responsible generation by empowering students in leadership roles, engaging them in hands-on activities, and including zero-waste instruction into the curriculum. Incentives and rewards encourage sustainable behaviors, while environmental awareness promotes long-term commitment to zero-waste methods.

Strategic Intervention on Self

Pertinent themes were identified based on Suggested Strategic Intervention on Self. Through a series of laborious and stringent

procedures in data analysis and interpretation and five (5) relevant themes were articulated.

Relevant Theme 1: Adopting and Practicing Personal Zero-Waste Habits

Participants underlined decreasing single-use plastics, composting, using eco-friendly items, and lowering paper consumption as important personal efforts. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Limiting single-use plastics, bringing reusable containers, or minimizing paper usage. Lastly, we can lead the charge through setting a positive example for students and colleagues to follow.” in lines Environmentalist #1 43, 44, and 45.

“For me, we must regularly practice zero-waste habits such as using reusable containers, reducing paper use, composting at home and school, leading by example by minimizing waste in daily routines and encouraging others to do the same.” in lines Environmentalist #2 88, 89, 90, and 91.

This is consistent with the findings of Steg and Vlek (2020), who claim that individual-level behavioral adjustments are critical for resolving environmental issues. Individuals can greatly reduce waste by implementing tiny, consistent activities. Schools and communities should provide resources and knowledge to assist people develop sustainable habits, such as reusable containers and composting tools.

Relevant Theme 2: Leadership Through Role Modeling

Participants highlighted leading by example and setting positive examples for peers and students. Bandura's (1977) social learning theory supports this idea, suggesting that individuals can influence others' behaviors through modeling. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“We can lead the charge through setting a positive example for students and colleagues to follow.” in lines Environmentalist #1 44 and 45.

“Dapat tayo ay maging model sa nasabing program sa pamamagitan ng pagpapakita ng dedikasyon at mga personal na aksyon, mula sa paggamit ng mga reusable na bagay hanggang sa pagtuturo sa iba tungkol sa kahalagahan ng paglilinis Ng kapaligiran, at kailangan tayo ay maging isang halimbawa para sa lahat. (We must be role models for the program by showing dedication and personal actions, from using reusable items to teaching others about the importance of cleaning the environment. We need to set an example for everyone.)” in lines Environmentalist #4 186, 187, 188, 189, 190, 191, 192, and 193.

Demonstrating commitment to sustainability encourages others to follow suit. Institutions can recognize and showcase individuals who consistently practice zero-waste behaviors to inspire wider adoption.

One of the most essential things a leader can do is set a good example for those who look up to them. Whether you're a CEO, a manager, or simply someone in a position of power, those who look up to you will draw their cues from your behavior. That is why it is critical to ensure that your actions are consistent with your statements, Brycy P. (2022).

Relevant Theme 3: Ongoing Learning and Self-Reflection

Participants stated that ongoing learning and self-reflection was practices of the students in school and continuous education on sustainability practices and reflecting on personal waste generation were identified as key strategies for self-improvement. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“We must regularly reflect on personal waste generation and find ways to further reduce it.” in lines Environmentalist #2 91, 92, and 93.

“Share your experiences and successes with others to inspire them to adopt similar practices. Continuously educate yourself on new waste management strategies and bring fresh ideas to the school community.” in lines Environmentalist #6 277, 278, and 279.

According to Stern et al. (2000) emphasize the importance of developing an internal value system for sustained behavior change. By staying informed and self-aware, individuals can refine their actions to be more impactful. Providing access to updated resources, workshops, and training programs on sustainability can help individuals stay engaged and motivated.

Reflecting on household garbage generation reveals that individuals play a big role in the amount of waste created. Personal experiences and observations show that everyday choices, such as purchasing products with excessive packaging or choosing single-use items, have a direct impact on the development of household garbage. Furthermore, a lack of adequate waste management procedures causes a buildup of rubbish in residences, affecting the overall waste disposal process. These observations highlight the essential need for improved knowledge and education about sustainable consumption patterns. Individuals must make conscious decisions to reduce, reuse, and recycle their garbage (Brodowicz, (2024).

Relevant Theme 4: Advocacy and Peer Inspiration

The participants also said that sharing personal successes and advocating for zero-waste principles in daily interactions were identified

as effective ways to inspire others. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Advocating for zero-waste principles in daily interaction with students and peers.” in lines Environmentalist #2 134 and 135.

“Practicing Zero Waste habits in your own life to inspire others and sharing personal stories and successes to motivate peers.” in lines Environmentalist #5 230, 231, and 232.

According to Deci and Ryan (2000), intrinsic motivation, combined with external advocacy, can create a ripple effect, motivating others to adopt similar behaviors. Schools and workplaces should encourage individuals to share their sustainability practices through storytelling, workshops, or peer discussions.

The UN-Habitat developed this advocacy toolbox and guide, "My Waste, Our Wealth" to aid local officials in sensitizing its people about waste management challenges and in fostering sustainable day-to-day habits that can help the county improve waste management in the long run. This advocacy toolkit and guide attempts to foster behavior change at the community level to achieve sustainable resource use and municipal solid waste management in cities. Waste management interventions should be accompanied by awareness and sensitization activities. It is critical that the community understands how the facility will operate technology will be involved, how they may benefit from it, and how their involvement is critical for it. To achieve achievement and reap the most benefits as stated by Borda (2020).

It was further emphasized by Borda (2020), utilizing broadcasting media to channel the key messages and increasing awareness on sustainable resources and waste management is another effective tool. These include: radio programs, newspapers, magazines and television programs. For instance, in Sao Paulo, Brazil, the publication of a monthly magazine, special radio and television programs are used to disseminate information about the municipality's source separation program. Celebrities, politicians and public leaders can be involved in the dissemination of such messages. While not everyone has a television, everyone has access to the radio. Radio programs can provide platforms for the community to obtain in-depth knowledge on waste management and to discuss issues concerning their neighborhood, with city authorities as well as national and international experts (including private sector and development organizations), while entertaining too. For example, studies on the effectiveness of radio awareness campaigns on sustainable resource and waste management in Juba (South Sudan) and Yobe State (Nigeria) revealed that compared to the years before the radio programs, the extent of random disposal of garbage by the population had reduced, as well as the regular occurrences of sicknesses such as diarrhoea, cholera and typhoid .

Relevant Theme 5: Fostering Environmental Awareness Through Teaching

Participants emphasized educating others about the importance of zero-waste practices and sharing innovative ideas. According to McKenzie-Mohr (2020) suggests that awareness campaigns and educational efforts are instrumental in fostering collective action. Institutions can encourage individuals to take active roles in environmental education, creating a community-wide impact through shared knowledge. These sentiments are reflected in the statements of the participants as follows:

“Pagtuturo sa iba tungkol sa kahalagahan ng paglilinis ng kapaligiran. (Teaching others about the importance of cleaning the environment.)” in lines Environmentalist #4 188, 189, 191, and 192.

“Continuously educate yourself on new waste management strategies and bring fresh ideas to the school community.)” in lines Environmentalist #6 278 and 279.

Similar study, also investigates the role of education in shaping environmental values, skills, and decision-making abilities that are essential for responsible ecological stewardship. In addition, the article investigates novel techniques and methodologies that might be used in educational programs to improve environmental literacy and promote active citizen participation in tackling environmental concerns. The study aims to look at the relationship between perception, attitude, and environmental behavior among higher education students specializing in subjects like electrical engineering, mechanics, and economics. The survey, which included 453 students from Ukrainian higher education institutions, used the Likert scale to assess their environmental education, perception, attitude, and conduct. Students that actively participate in academic education demonstrate engagement in environmental efforts such as volunteering, event participation, and recycling, as well as a deep interest in green AI-Mull, Ari, & Koç (2022).

The themes reveal that personal commitment to zero-waste practices, combined with advocacy and education, can drive meaningful change. Role modeling, self-reflection, and continuous learning enhance individual contributions to sustainability efforts. Institutions should support these interventions by creating environments that enable and reward personal responsibility and advocacy.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the researcher found that zero-waste initiative is very effective and students at Lambayong National High School are strongly supportive of the said initiative. When it comes to environmental literacy, these data demonstrated that students are environmentally knowledgeable, has strong positive attitude towards the environment, and practicing sustainably pertaining to solid waste management in the school and community. Additionally, students' achievement on environmental literacy is at the average level. The student participation on the zero-waste initiative has significant effect on environmental literacy achievement. Further, the extent

of the zero-waste initiative has effect on environmental literacy in terms of knowledge, attitude, and practices. Finally, the intervention to continue the program is suggested by developing the established organization, obtaining full support from the LGU, and collecting waste on a regular basis in school and community.

References

- Abdel-Shafy, H. & Mansour, M. (2018). Solid waste issue: Sources, composition, disposal, recycling, and valorization. *Egyptian Journal of Petroleum*, 27, 1275-1290.
- Ariyadi, F., & Afriandi, F. (2024). The Role of Government and Community Collaboration in the Implementation of Waste Management Policies in Palu City. *Journal of Management and Administration Provision*, 4(2), 179–187. <https://doi.org/10.55885/jmap.v4i2.382>
- Coracero, E. E., Gallego, R. J., Frago, K. J. M., & Gonzales, R. J. R. (2021). A Long-Standing problem: A review on the solid waste management in the Philippines. *Indonesian Journal of Social and Environmental Issues (IJSEI)*, 2(3), 213–220. <https://doi.org/10.47540/ijsei.v2i3.144>
- Creeger, Allison (2017). Public Perception of Leadership in the Municipal Solid Waste Sector" (2017). *Environmental Studies Undergraduate Student Theses*. 202
- Cruz, R. a. O., & Nabor, A. P., Jr. (2022). Pupils' awareness, knowledge, attitude and practice of School-Based Solid Waste Management in a public elementary school in the Philippines. *University of Wah Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.56220/uwjss2022/0501/01>
- Kihila, J. M., Wernsted, K., & Kaseva, M. (2021). Waste segregation and potential for recycling -A case study in Dar es Salaam City, Tanzania. *Sustainable Environment*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/27658511.2021.1935532>
- Rahmandoust, A., Hafezalkotob, A., Rahmani Parchikolaei, B. et al. Government intervention in municipal waste collection with a sustainable approach: a robust bi-level problem. *Environ Dev Sustain* 25, 3323–3351 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02181-1>

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